

EVALUATION OF THE INDUSTRIAL SECTOR AND ITS DEVELOPMENT TRENDS

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Annotation : *This in the article industry sector and his development trends about thought reviews statement reported . In recent years, the country has taken comprehensive measures to develop the textile, garment, leather, footwear and fur industries of the light industry, expand the range and types of finished products, as well as provide comprehensive support for investment and exports. increased. activities of industrial enterprises. Increased competition in world markets, the development of technology and the reduction of production costs by foreign manufacturers require the development of additional measures for the development of these industries.*

The key word : Textile industry , textiles and tikuv-trikotaj products , market , demand , re performance , ready product , export.

INTRODUCTION

Republic Presidential Decree No. PF-5285 of December 14, 2017 with " Uztextile Industry " Uzbekistan textile and tikuv-trikotaj industry enterprises association formed reported . Unga appropriate textile products size and quality The species is also expanding . Modern fashion industry trends and directions based on functional remove to the process eng good design developments is entered . In Uzbekistan textile and tikuv-trikotaj products functional extractor leading businesses association muttasil areas of improvement and all our country economy upgrade , social issues hal reach , population employment supply , new the work seats to create suitable contribution adds .

Table 1

Uzbekistan gross internal product and textile industry growth rates ,
trln . sum _

Indicators	years									
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
YaIM	120.1	144.5	177.2	210.2	242.5	302.5	406.6	511.8	602.5	734.5
Production capacity	57.6	70.6	84.2	97.6	111.9	148.8	235.3	322.5	367.1	451.6
Processing industry	43.6	55.3	67.1	77.1	89.8	117.7	189.6	254.8	304.7	375.1
textile products	7.6	8.9	10.8	13.2	13.3	16.8	24.8	29.9	36.2	51.5

Today, textile enterprises play an important role in the production process of the republic. One of the most pressing issues is the regulation of the quality of products produced by textile enterprises - cotton fiber, yarn, dyed yarn, yarn, knitwear, silk at the level of world standards. In order to solve this problem, in recent years, textile enterprises have been introducing new enterprises, equipment and machinery that meet the demand. The Government of the Republic has adopted decisions on further development of the textile industry, including: - "Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021." Demand for textile products in our country is extremely high, and to meet these needs, joint ventures are being established on the basis of agreements with developed countries in the textile industry (Decree of 2017). - Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 16, 2019 No PP-4453 "On measures to further develop the light industry and stimulate the production of finished products" (2019). - Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 14, 2017 No 15285 "On measures to accelerate the development of the textile and clothing industry." There are a number of factors that help to improve the organizational and economic activities of textile enterprises. At

present, financial, labor and material indicators depend on efficiency indicators in increasing the efficiency of many textile enterprises.

METHODS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

In order to develop the production of products that meet modern market requirements, it is necessary to modernize the economic potential of enterprises, ie the basic means of production, improve the skills of workers, radically improve working conditions, the widespread introduction of modern technologies. introduction of technologies into the production process, systematic study of market requirements and effective use of human resources. . In our country, serious attention is paid to increasing the share of finished products in exports. Significant work is being done in this direction in the light industry. The results of the analysis show that if in 2015 the country processed 336 thousand tons, in 2016 - 400 thousand tons, in 2017 - 468 thousand tons of cotton fiber, in 2018 - about 706 thousand tons, and in 2019 - about 706 thousand tons. processed. , 714 thousand tons of cotton fiber were processed, which is 100 thousand tons more than in previous years. In the future, it is planned to fully process the produced cotton fiber, which will significantly increase the additional cost of the finished product.

The revival of work in this area will increase the volume of finished products and value-added foreign exchange earnings, create new jobs. We will consider the dynamics of the volume of products produced and exported by the enterprises of the Association "Uztextile Industry".

In addition, in 2021, the enterprises of the Uztekimachilik sanoat Association will produce 670.0 thousand tons of yarn and 460.0 million square meters of finished yarn. m. It is planned to increase the production of knitted fabrics to 160.0 thousand tons. tons, garments and knitwear - up to 630.0 million units, hosiery - up to 260 million pairs. It is important to analyze the content and principles of the ongoing reforms in this area, as well as to study the theoretical and methodological foundations of the processes of modernization, technical and technological renewal.

In this regard, the meaning of the term modernization has been interpreted differently. In particular, in the economic literature and dictionaries it is described

as follows: , adaptation to technological processes. In recent years, the country has taken comprehensive measures to develop the textile, garment, leather, footwear and fur industries. Development of light industry, expansion of the range and range of products and comprehensive support for investment and export activities of enterprises in the sector, ie the share of light industry enterprises in the export of finished garments. exempted from paying value added tax.

Table 2

The main technical and economic indicators of the Association of Textile Industry for 2018-2021

No.	Indicators	unit of measurement	years			
			2018	2019	2020	2021
one	Ip	A thousand tones	410.0	575.2	629.8	697.4
2	mato	million sq.m.	235.5	268.3	406.0	463.2
	Knitted cloth	A thousand tones	76.1	111.2	119.6	168.2
4	Finished products	Million pieces	312.1	432.0	548.1	632.1
five	Socks	Million bugs	168.9	197.3	257.0	267.7

The necessary legal framework and favorable conditions for the further development of the textile and clothing industry in the country have been formed, the attraction of additional funds, the great attention paid to the diversification of the production process allows to increase production. Work is underway to improve the mechanism of quality management in light industry enterprises, in particular, to improve the composition and tasks of the working group on "Quality Management and Monitoring" in industry enterprises. Today, the light industry is developing rapidly. In these sectors, all opportunities are being used to support private sector initiatives and new projects. diversification of the production process, which allows to increase production capacity. Work is underway to improve the quality

management mechanism in light industry enterprises, in particular, industry enterprises, to improve the composition and tasks of the working group on "Quality Management and Monitoring". Today, the light industry is developing rapidly. In these sectors, all opportunities are being used to support private sector initiatives and new projects. diversification of the production process, which allows to increase production capacity. Work is underway to improve the quality management mechanism in light industry enterprises, in particular, industry enterprises, to improve the composition and tasks of the working group on "Quality Management and Monitoring". Today, the light industry is developing rapidly. In these sectors, all opportunities are being used to support private sector initiatives and new projects.

Table 3

Export indicators of the Association of Textile Industry for 2018-2021

No.	Indicators	unit of measurement	years			
			2018	2019	2020	2021
one	Ip	A thousand tones	282.3	381.1	455.4	437.2
2	mato	million sq.m.	184.5	215.5	296.5	357.5
3	Knitted cloth	A thousand tones	15.2	20.4	33.2	43.9
4	Finished products	Million pieces	424.8	486.3	648.0	1499.8
five	Socks	Million bugs	47.0	74.6	119.8	172.4

Textile industry Uzbekistan economy for strategic importance has _ He is constant as evolving to consumers high quality modern products offer is doing . Current at the time world in the market textile products which was demand , uni functional issue focused countries economy for importance and role already of oil positions with compared . Our country until recently cotton raw materials export so would come . Gradually , new technology and processes current so cotton _ fiber functional issue we passed and his in export share from year to year decreased is

growing and Uzbekistan to go to 2021 complete again performance and ready product functional remove in favor of export Entirely stop is planning .

Textile world consumption goods functional in the output eng wide applied . Of Uzbekistan ecological clean , 100 percent natural raw material with providing its own rich resources , light industry development years created many state and private businesses This is also the case of the industry development service is doing . , in particular equipment and functional remove powers has which was textile _ , all international standards answer giving , Uzbek textile industry world markets effect spend to receive strategic resource level lift opportunity gives _

Today kunda 7,000 in Uzbekistan more than light industry enterprises activity is running . They are UZTEX GROUP among CIS countries textile products functional extractor leading , vertical integrated functional extractor is _ UZTEX GROUP functional remove powers of cotton textile products all species : gray and painted of threads all species , gray and painted flax fabrics , ready knitwear , socks , knitwear products functional remove opportunity gives _ Our company 11 years ago previously painted "UZTEX CHIRCHIK" gauze functional remove on first factory to work down business _ initiatives state by supported , in particular , the tax and customs privileges , privileged conditions loans and other support that we feel given due to 11 years in our country formerly known as UZTEX CHIRCHIK painted mato functional extractor enterprise to work lowered . Uzbekistan along from 13 factories located consists of strong functional remove to the group became .

45 thousand per hectare more than cotton planting clusters due to the development of UZTEX GROUP release all stages - cotton fiber planting , harvesting , cleaning and preparation , gray ip preparation , painted kalava and flax functional until release which was all steps own into received complete technological tsiklni control does . ready products betting , marking and packaging _ Vertical integration is, without a doubt , the ultimate of the product high quality effect does .

Today kunga up to UZTEX GROUP enterprises functional remove capacity 45 thousand tons more than har kind of kind of gray kalava , of which 18 thousand

tons painted kalava , 12 thousand tons gray knitwear , 7 thousand tons painted knitwear mato , 2 min tons gauze and 250 thousand tons gauze _ rotation click with 41 thousand tons circle kalava , 3.5 thousand tons blown kalava , 20 million pieces ready knitwear , 70 million pairs socks , 12 million pieces terry and 3 thousand tons painted cotton fiber .

Ours our customers - fashion chakana in the market large network operators - branded chakana trade requirements complete answer giving products they get .

Conclusion :

Current at the time new materials and new technology functional remove methodical and information supply functional exit zarurati innovative properties information base functional exit scientific development functions to one turned into cause is happening . New technological processes and of materials efficiency evaluation zarurati industry new materials and products functional remove with depending on investment projects substantiation opportunity gives _

Textile and light in industry new materials and technology efficiency evaluation methodical issues functional exit necessity about our conclusions textiles , knitwear , sewing , footwear and fur in the industry applied radical changes and well-known classic technology with based on .

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